

Microfluidic-Assisted Synthesis of Uniform Polymer-Stabilized Silver Colloids

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Abstract

We report the controlled synthesis of polymer-stabilized silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) by using microfluidic devices. The microfluidic-based method enabled the preparation of sub-50 nm AgNPs which are much more homogenous compared to those produced in batch reactors where the control over flow and mixing conditions was not performed. The concentration of the silver precursor (silver nitrate - AgNO_3) can be tuned to reach smaller or larger nanoparticles, although within a fairly narrow range. Regardless of the polymeric shell, the reducing agent concentration influences the size and polydispersity of the manufactured silver colloids, and relatively lower amounts allow for the manufacturing of more homogeneous nanoparticles. Notably, the use of the block copolymer PEO-*b*-P2VP as stabilizing agent leads to larger nanoparticles (23-51 nm) compared to those stabilized by PVP (7-14 nm) as possibly linked to different arrangements of the polymer chains at the interface between the precursor solutions. The produced AgNPs are highly uniform, with size distribution width influenced by the polymer concentration (FWHM < 100 nm were determined at higher concentrations), although this variable does not have a distinguished effect on the final size of the manufactured colloids. Overall, we provide relevant new knowledge within the framework of polymer-stabilized AgNPs since a variety of other polymer chains can be probed, possibly with different outcomes regarding the final particle size. The reported findings can thus guide to significant advances towards the manufacturing of highly homogeneous polymer-coated metallic colloids, particularly when a target size is required.

1. Introduction

The outstanding optical, chemical and biocide properties of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) drove their use in a myriad of applications including the wide fields of sensors,[1] catalysis[2] and environmental treatments.[3] The unique antimicrobial properties of silver colloids[4–6] also made them very popular in coatings for medical devices (surgical clothes, dressings, etc.).[7,8] They additionally find applicability in more complex strategies such as *in-vivo* imaging[9,10] and tumor therapies.[11] The potential applications of AgNPs are linked to their structural features (shape, size, size distribution, surface charge, etc.) which relevantly influence their efficacy as mainly determined by the overall contact area, plasmon band energy and quantum size effects.[12] The structural parameters of silver colloids are usually linked by the chosen strategy for their manufacturing. In this framework, one still faces the challenge of producing inorganic colloids with control over particle size and narrow size distribution. Unfortunately, the most practical and straightforward methods for the synthesis of noble metal nanoparticles frequently lead to broad size distributions. This potentially reduces their efficacy which is usually size-dependent.[13]

The typical inhomogeneity of metallic colloids prepared in batch reactors are primarily attributed to the highly heterogeneous flow and mixing conditions. The control over the synthesis ambient is therefore of due relevance towards the manufacturing of well-defined nanomaterials, possibly enhancing their effectiveness. Accordingly, homogeneous reaction environments with controllable parameters have been recently introduced for the synthesis of uniform colloidal materials. This can be for instance reached by the use of microfluidic devices.[14] The microfluidic approach refers to methods with precise control and manipulation of fluids that are geometrically constrained typically in the micrometer scale in which capillary penetration governs

mass transport. Generally, microfluidic devices enable the preparation of particles with controllable size [15] and particularly, narrow size distribution.[16] The microfluidic devices are usually found in multiphase or single-phase flow configurations.[17] In the first case, a segmented flow is produced by the contact of immiscible solvents, and the flow takes the form of droplets or slugs, for instance. The single-phase flow systems are simpler and the continuous laminar flow streams of fluids are produced through microchannels, and the nanoparticle formation takes place without the presence of immiscible segments. In one hand, the single-phase laminar flow reactors are easier to be implemented and do not require auxiliary fluids to reach the desired flow regime. On the other hand, they are commonly more affected by fouling problems.[18] The segmented flow reactors create increased interfacial area and are characterized by shorter transfer distances which usually lead to narrower particle size distributions. [19] Regardless of the category, these microreactors have been considered promising platforms allowing better control over mass transport and the possibility to tune precisely particle size and size distribution.[20] Additionally, the flow characteristics in microchannels are also affected by the geometry of the microfluidic devices, which also impact the final nanoparticle characteristics. The reduction of helix diameter in a curved microreactor conducted for instance to the formation of smaller and narrower AgNPs as attributed to the onset of transversal flows and radial mixing.[21] The device configuration can indeed lead to opposite trends such as evidenced in the manufacturing of AgNPs using only a coaxial flow reactor [22] or coaxial flow reactor combined with a split and recombine (SAR) mixer. [23]

Concerning the chemical point of view, one of the easiest wet methods to manufacture AgNPs refers to the reduction of silver ions (from a chemical precursor such as silver nitrate - AgNO_3) by a reducing agent such as borohydride (from sodium

borohydride - NaBH₄) in the presence of stabilizers (for instance, hydrophilic polymer chains). This strategy has been recently applied by us [24] where we demonstrated successfully the production of polymer-stabilized AgNPs with distinct structural and biocide features.[25] Nevertheless, despite our efforts, the employed approaches led to the production of fairly polydisperse samples as evidenced by TEM (transmission electron microscopy), DLS (dynamic light scattering) and UV-Vis spectroscopy measurements. Taking into account these considerations, we made a step further to investigate the manufacturing of AgNPs within microfluidic devices. They were based on single-phase flow systems and a variety of synthesis parameters have been evaluated towards the manufacturing of highly uniform AgNPs. The microfluidic approach evidenced to be a robust platform to finely tune the size and uniformity of silver colloids which is usually required for particular applications.

2. Methodology

2.1. Chemicals

Silver nitrate (AgNO₃) and sodium borohydride (NaBH₄) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The stabilizing polymer PVP (polyvinylpyrrolidone) was also purchased from Sigma-Aldrich whereas PEO-*b*-P2VP (poly(ethylene oxide)-*b*-poly(2-vinyl pyridine)) was purchased from Polymer Source Inc. The water was previously pretreated with Milli-Q[®] Plus System (Millipore Corporation). The molecular structures of the polymer stabilizing agents are portrayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Molecular structure of polyvinylpyrrolidone (left) and poly(ethylene oxide)-*b*-poly(2-vinyl pyridine) (right).

The number average molecular weight and molecular weight distribution for PVP and PEO-*b*-P2VP are respectively $M_n = 40000 \text{ g.mol}^{-1}$; $M_w/M_n = 2.0$ and $M_n = 21000$ - b - 13500 g.mol^{-1} ; $M_w/M_n = 1.1$.

2.2. Microfluidic Devices

The PDMS microfluidic device with main focusing channel of $150 \mu\text{m} \times 150 \mu\text{m}$ (depth \times width) was fabricated by using standard photo lithography.[26] The microchannels were design using the AutoCAD software (Autodesk) and printed on a mask foil with a UV-absorbent ink (JD Photo Data). A negative photoresist (SU-8, Microchem Co.) was spin-coated onto a silicon wafer and a mask aligner (Süss Mikro Tec) was used to impart the printed microchannel structure from the mask foil into the photoresist generating the silicon wafer pattern. Afterwards, polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS, Sylgard 184 kit, Dow Corning Corp.) and the curing agent were mixed (10:1 *v/v*) and transferred to the silicon wafer pattern. The mixture was then degassed under vacuum for 2h and then baked at $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4h. Afterwards, the inlet and outlet holes were punched, and individual pieces were bonded onto a glass slide after 30s activation of PDMS surface by O_2 plasma treatment. The PDMS microfluidic device was stored for 24h at $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ prior to use. The glass micromixer chip with a main focusing channel of $125 \mu\text{m} \times 350 \mu\text{m}$ (depth \times width) was purchased ready to be used from Dolomite (United Kingdom).

2.3 Manufacturing of the Polymer-Stabilized AgNPs by Microfluidics

The production of the polymer-stabilized silver colloids has been conducted in the microfluidic devices. The microfluidic devices made in glass or PDMS contain microchannels thereby providing required conditions for the manufacturing of AgNPs controllably. The silver precursor (AgNO_3 aqueous solutions) was pumped through the central channel of the microfluidic devices whereas the mixtures containing the reducing agent (NaBH_4) along with the stabilizing polymers were pumped through the side channels. The concentrations of the chemicals were variable parameters and they are given throughout the manuscript. The aqueous solutions were pumped to the microfluidic devices using two independent NE-1002X Microfluidics Syringe Pump controlled *via* PC software. The flow rates were variable parameters ranging respectively from 1500-6000 $\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and 10-100 $\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ for the glass and PMDS microfluidic devices. The majority of the experiments were performed by keeping fixed the flow rate ratio at 3 (flow rates of 2000 and 6000 $\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ respectively in the central and side channels). The polymer-stabilized silver colloids were also prepared manually without any control over the mixing conditions for comparison purposes.

2.4. Characterization of the Polymer-Stabilized Silver Colloids

Dynamic Light Scattering: The dynamic light scattering (DLS) data were acquired using a ZetaSizer Nano ZS90 apparatus. The averaged intensity autocorrelation functions were evaluated using the non-negative least squares (NNLS) analysis implemented in the Zetasizer software therefore resulting in distribution of sizes converted from distributions of times using the Stokes-Einstein relation:

$$R_H = \frac{k_B T q^2}{6\pi\eta} \tau \quad (1)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature, η is the viscosity of the solvent, τ is the mean relaxation time related to the diffusion of the nanoparticles and q is the scattering vector. The volume-weighted distributions of sizes are given in the manuscript, which were generated from original intensity-weighted distributions.

Electrophoretic Light Scattering (ELS): ELS data were also acquired using a ZetaSizer Nano ZS90 apparatus. They were useful to determine the average zeta potential (ζ) of the polymer-stabilized AgNPs. The values of electrophoretic mobility (U_E) were measured and converted to values of ζ -potential (mV) using the Henry's equation:

$$U_E = \frac{2 \varepsilon \zeta f(ka)}{3 \eta} \quad (2)$$

where ε is the dielectric constant of the medium (water) and η its viscosity with $f(ka)$, the Henry's function, calculated through the Smoluchowski approximation - $f(ka) = 1.5$.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM): The polymer-stabilized AgNPs were imaged by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a Tecnai G2 Spirit Twin 120kV (FEI, Czech Republic) microscope. Two- μ L of the aqueous solutions were dropped onto a copper TEM microscopic grid (400 mesh) coated with a thin and electron-transparent carbon film. The excess of samples was removed by touching the bottom of the grid with filtering paper. This fast removal of the solution was performed after 1 min of sedimentation in order to minimize oversaturation during the drying process. The samples were left to dry completely at room temperature and then

observed by TEM. The reported size distributions were built by measuring 130 particles using ImageJ and adjusted with a Gaussian distribution equation to obtain the average sizes and standard deviations.

UV-Vis Spectroscopy: UV-vis spectroscopy data were acquired by using a Thermo Scientific Evolution 220 UV-visible spectrophotometer. The spectral resolution for wavelength scanning was 1.0 nm. The measurements were performed by using a quartz cell with optical path length of 10 mm.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Influence of the Mixing Conditions

The microfluidic-assisted synthesis regards the manufacturing of the polymer-stabilized silver colloids in micrometric channels. The main goal of such methodology is to provide better control over mixing conditions and therefore, the control over particle properties, particularly the size and size distribution. We manufactured the polymer-stabilized metallic colloids using two different microfluidic devices fabricated in PDMS (polydimethylsiloxane) or glass. They are portrayed in Figure 2.

Figure 2. (Top) Images of the microfluidic devices made in glass (Left) and PDMS (Right) used in the manufacturing of the polymer-stabilized AgNPs, along with a schematic representation of the whole microfluidic setup (Bottom).

The glass microfluidic device (Figure 2 - Left) has a Y-shaped layout with main channel width $w = 350 \mu\text{m}$, whereas the PDMS microfluidic device (Figure 2 - Right) has a T-shaped configuration with $w = 150 \mu\text{m}$. Regardless of the employed microfluidic device, the central stream contained a silver nitrate solution (central channel) whereas the lateral channels contained a sodium borohydride solution along with the stabilizing polymers. The precursor solutions were delivered to the microfluidic devices by using syringe pumps such as schematically represented at the bottom of Figure 2. The flow rates of the AgNO_3 and NaBH_4 /polymer solutions were initially variable parameters. The configuration of the microfluidic devices resulted in hydrodynamic pressure exerted by the flow of the lateral channels into the flow of the central channel, and the appearance of a hydrodynamic flow focusing along the central channel towards the outlet. The continuous flow of aqueous solutions in the microchannels enables the nucleation and growth of the silver colloids at the edges of the solutions *via* the diffusion of the reactants across the laminar flow streams. The formation of AgNPs in microfluidic devices presumably follows the mechanism proposed by LaMer and Dinegar.[27] The contact of the precursor (Ag^+) and reducing agent (BH_4^-) enables the nucleation of nanoparticles and further growth *via* the coalescence of clusters in the presence of the stabilizing polymers PVP or PEO-*b*-P2VP. The synthesis of nearly-monodisperse AgNPs requires the controlled assembly of Ag clusters during the nucleation step. This process must be fast and therefore, the contact of Ag^+ ions with BH_4^- must be quick and homogenous. The use of the microfluidic device inhibits the reaction in silver nitrate rich zones therefore conducting to the formation of smaller nanoparticles compared to those prepared in a batch reactor, without the control over the mixing conditions.[25]

The Figure 3 reports UV-vis, DLS and TEM data concerning the synthesis of PVP-stabilized AgNPs using the glass and PDMS microfluidic devices. The concentration of the reactants was kept fixed whereas the flow rates were variable parameters. The data highlight negligible differences in the structural features of the fabricated silver colloids regardless of the employed microfluidic device, thus meaning that the final products are similar. The quantitative data are provided in Table 1 and they point out fairly small PVP-stabilized AgNPs ($D_H \sim 12-14$ nm) with $\lambda_{\max} \sim 400$ nm. Additionally, the ζ -potential (~ -20 mV) and the values of the full width at half maximum - FWHM (~ 100 nm) are also similar. The representative TEM image underlines the production of homogenous and spherical or quasi-spherical nanoparticles. Considering the high degree of similarity between the assemblies, we have proceeded with the investigations only by using the glass microfluidic device due its versatility regarding stability and production yield. The glass chip was less prone to fouling, keeping the laminar flow stable for a longer period and therefore producing higher amounts of colloidal silver. The manufacturing method was evidenced to be highly reproducible as reported for selected samples in the Supporting Information File (Figures S1-S2).

Figure 3. UV-vis absorption spectra (top) and size distribution weighted by volume (middle) for AgNPs@PVP prepared using different microfluidic devices according to the legends. TEM image (bottom) of the nanoparticles prepared using the PDMS microfluidic device along with respective size distribution histogram ($[\text{AgNO}_3] = 0.94 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$; $[\text{PVP}] = 0.5 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$; $[\text{NaBH}_4] = 3.0 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$).

Table 1. Manufacturing conditions and structural features of PVP-stabilized AgNPs produced in different microfluidic devices as determined by UV-vis spectroscopy and light scattering measurements.

Microfluidic Chip	Flow Rate Ratio	D_H (nm)	ζ (mV)	λ_{max} (nm)	FWHM (nm)
PDMS	10	12.0 ± 0.7	-18 ± 2	404.4 ± 0.9	113 ± 2
Glass	4	14.4 ± 0.8	-18 ± 4	402 ± 1	118 ± 4
Glass	3	13.2 ± 0.4	-26 ± 2	401.8 ± 0.5	111 ± 1
Glass	2	13.8 ± 0.5	-20 ± 3	402.2 ± 0.8	113 ± 3

$[AgNO_3] = 0.94 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$; $[PVP] = 0.5 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$; $[NaBH_4] = 3.0 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$

We have also investigated the influence of the flow rate ratio in the structural features of the PVP-stabilized AgNPs. These assemblies were produced using the glass microfluidic device. The data summarized in Table 1 do not suggest significant influence within the assessed range (from 2 to 4). Indeed, the PDMS microfluidic device required a particularly higher flow rate ratio (10) otherwise the narrower microchannel was rapidly clogged. Nevertheless, the structural features of the silver colloids are highly similar to those fabricated by using the glass microfluidic device. The data suggest that, in the probed range, the flow rate ratio does not seem to remarkably influence the structural features of the polymer-stabilized silver colloids. This has been also observed regardless of the stabilizing polymer, $AgNO_3$ or $NaBH_4$ concentrations (not shown here for brevity). Accordingly, such empirical evidences suggest that the mixing between the precursor solutions is faster than the timescale for the nucleation and growth of the silver colloids and thus, their structural features are independent of the mixing time (τ_{mix}) which in a continuous microfluidic channel can be estimated by using the following equation:[28]

$$\tau_{mix} \approx \frac{w^2}{9(1+R)^2 D} \quad (3)$$

with w , D and R being respectively the channel width, diffusivity of the solvent and the side-to-central channels flow rate ratio. Taking into account the dimension of the channel width ($w = 150 \mu\text{m}$ - PDMS; $w = 350 \mu\text{m}$ - glass microfluidic device), diffusivity of water $D \sim 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ and flow rate ratio in the range from 2 to 10 depending on the microfluidic device, τ_{mix} was estimated to be in the range $\sim 20\text{-}1500$ ms. Considering that the size of the produced AgNPs is reported to be flow rate-independent (therefore independent of τ_{mix}), the AgNPs formation is supposed to take place at the timescale of hundreds of ms. The formation of AgNPs involves the appearance of silver nuclei (nucleation) and further growth. Indeed, the synthesis of gold nanoparticles by using NaBH_4 as reducing agent was evidenced to occur in two steps where the reduction of the metal precursor (HAuCl_4) and the formation of small clusters take place in less than 200 ms, and this is followed by particle growth *via* coalescence in the time scale of a few seconds.[29] The kinetics of AgNPs formation has been similarly investigated. The process was evidenced to be initially analogous and within the same timescale.[30] Taking into account the related literature, τ_{mix} values estimated by using the Equation 3, and the empirical data herein reported, the mixing time is likely to be faster than the nanoparticle formation.

Although the results do not suggest the influence of the flow rate ratio in the structural features of the manufactured silver colloids, the highly homogenous environment conducted to remarkably more homogenous assemblies. This can be evidenced by comparing the data reported in Figure 3 with those reported in Figure 4 where the UV-vis spectroscopy pattern and TEM image of silver colloids prepared manually without any control over the mixing conditions are reported (the reactants concentrations were kept fixed). The TEM image highlights nano-sized colloids highly heterogeneous in size, sometimes with irregular shape. This is also supported by the

asymmetrical UV-vis profile. Indeed, the highly heterogeneous feature of AgNPs stabilized by the same polymers as synthesized in a batch reactor, and therefore without controlling the mixing conditions, has been also previously evidenced by us.[25] Truthfully, this was the main motivation to perform the current investigation. Accordingly, the data confirm the relevant role of a homogenous environment towards the production of more uniform nanoparticles although the influence of the flow ratio in the final characteristics of the manufactured silver colloids has not been clearly observed.

Figure 4. UV-vis absorption spectrum (top) and TEM image along with respective size distribution histogram (bottom) for AgNPs@PVP prepared manually without control

over the mixing conditions ($[\text{AgNO}_3] = 0.94 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$; $[\text{PVP}] = 0.5 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$; $[\text{NaBH}_4] = 3.0 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$).

Taking into account these previous evidences, the further investigations have been conducted by using an optimized flow rate ratio ($R = 3$) and all the remaining measurements have been recorded by keeping fixed such experimental variable. This has been chosen empirically in order to reduce fouling which is particularly challenging in microfluidic devices due to their small dimensions. Nevertheless, fouling could be notably reduced in the time scale of the manufacturing protocol ($\sim 5 \text{ min}$) by using respectively $2000 \text{ }\mu\text{L.h}^{-1}$ and $6000 \text{ }\mu\text{L.h}^{-1}$ as the flow rates of the central and side channels. Yet, whenever fouling has been visually observed, the microfluidic device was cleaned by using diluted 1:2 piranha etch for 20 min.

3.2. Influence of the Silver Precursor Concentration

The influence of the silver nitrate concentration with regard to the microfluidic-assisted synthesis of the AgNPs has been evaluated by using two different stabilizers (PVP or PEO-*b*-P2VP). The UV-vis spectroscopy data for both sets of nanoparticles are provided in Figure 5 (top).

Figure 5. UV-vis absorption spectra (top) and size distributions weighted by volume (bottom) for AgNPs@PVP (left) and AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP (right) prepared by using different starting $AgNO_3$ concentrations according to the legend.

The average values of wavelength at maximum absorption (λ_{max}) and the full width at half maximum absorption (FWHM) are provided in Table 2. These parameters were useful to evaluate the structural features of the polymer-stabilized nanoparticles. Typically, λ_{max} reflects the size of the silver colloids where larger sizes shift λ_{max} to longer values (red shift), and the values of FWHM reflect the particle size distribution where the smaller the value the more homogenous the nanoparticles. The quantitative analysis of size distributions could be also assessed *via* the Cumulant analysis of the autocorrelation functions acquired by DLS. Nevertheless, light scattering is heavily

weighted by particle size, which is particularly relevant in the analysis of fairly small particles such as in the current case. We therefore preferred to analyze the homogeneity of the samples based on UV-vis data since light absorption is an incoherent process, therefore with no interference between scattered waves. The UV-vis profiles as well as the quantitative data reported in Table 2 are consistent and it can be noticed a shift in λ_{\max} towards larger values as AgNO_3 concentration increases.

Table 2. Structural features as determined by UV-vis spectroscopy and light scattering measurements for polymer-stabilized AgNPs produced in a glass microfluidic device at different starting concentrations of the silver ion (AgNO_3) precursor ($[\text{PVP}] = 0.5 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$; $[\text{PEO-}b\text{-P2VP}] = 0.02 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$ $[\text{NaBH}_4] = 3.0 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$).

AgNO_3 concentration (mmol.L^{-1})	D_{H} (nm)	ζ (mV)	λ_{\max} (nm)	FWHM (nm)
AgNPs@PVP				
0.24	6.9 ± 0.2	-25 ± 3	394.0 ± 0.6	139 ± 4
0.47	7.4 ± 0.2	-28 ± 3	396.9 ± 0.4	125 ± 3
0.71	8.2 ± 0.3	-21 ± 3	399.1 ± 0.4	115 ± 1
0.94	13.2 ± 0.4	-26 ± 2	401.8 ± 0.5	111 ± 1
AgNPs@PEO-<i>b</i>-P2VP				
0.24	23 ± 1	$+6 \pm 1$	404 ± 1	77 ± 1
0.47	30 ± 1	$+12 \pm 3$	406.0 ± 0.5	66 ± 1
0.71	38 ± 2	$+7 \pm 1$	413 ± 2	103 ± 2
0.94	43 ± 1	$+8 \pm 2$	420 ± 1	114 ± 4

The value of λ_{\max} migrates from 394.0 nm to 401.8 nm (AgNPs@PVP) and from 404 nm to 420 nm (AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP) in the evaluated concentration range. This is attributed to a quantum size effect where the band has a bathochromic shift as the nanoparticle size becomes bigger. It therefore suggests that larger AgNPs are produced when higher amounts of the silver precursor are used. Indeed, this has been also confirmed by dynamic light scattering (the data are provided at the bottom of Figure 5).

The size increase driven by higher silver ion concentration is presumably caused by the higher collision frequency between silver nuclei therefore leading to AgNPs embracing higher amounts of silver atoms. The behavior has been similarly observed in the manufacturing of AgNPs in a microfluidic coaxial flow reactor.[22] Hitherto, although the trend is clear, the difference in their dimension is not remarkable. This has been also confirmed by TEM imaging (Figure 6) despite the much smaller number of probed particles. The TEM images confirm the influence of the starting Ag^+ concentration in the final size of the assemblies. They also underscore that the PVP-stabilized AgNPs are smaller than those stabilized by PEO-*b*-P2VP in agreement with the data reported in Table 2 where longer values of λ_{max} and bigger values of R_{H} are reported for AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP. The behavior can be linked, at least to some extent, to the structural organization of the PEO-*b*-P2VP block copolymer chains into a fraction of micellar aggregates which possibly increase the interface viscosity leading to a reduction in the diffusion rate thereby increasing the mixing time and consequently, the particle size. We underline that, by comparing TEM and DLS data, the mean particle diameters determined from the TEM images are smaller than those monitored by DLS. The discrepancies are expected because the DLS data are weighted by volume whereas TEM gives number-average diameters. Additionally, the TEM imaging allows mainly the visualization of the silver cores while the polymer shells are hardly seen. Thus, TEM data usually undersize relative to DLS.

Figure 6. TEM images of AgNPs@PVP (top) and AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP (bottom) prepared at different starting AgNO₃ concentrations (a and c: 0.24 mmol.L⁻¹; b and d: 0.94 mmol.L⁻¹).

Additionally, besides larger AgNPs, there can be noticed a consistent trend with regard to the values of FWHM for AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP. The values point out less uniform silver colloids as the AgNO₃ concentration increases. This is visually evidenced by looking at the UV-vis profiles and at the quantitative data reported in Table 2. The values of FWHM are linked to the size distribution of the metallic colloids

and they are higher than 100 nm when the AgNPs were synthesized starting from AgNO₃ concentrations of 0.71 and 0.94 mmol.L⁻¹. They are considerably bigger than those determined for starting AgNO₃ concentrations of 0.47 and 0.24 mmol.L⁻¹ meaning that narrower size distributions are reached when the concentration of the silver precursor is reduced. Indeed, values of FWHM below 100 nm are found for noble metal nanoparticles with high degree of homogeneity whereas larger values are assigned to reasonably polydisperse samples.[31–33] This trend is also supported by the TEM data reported in Figure 6. The size distribution of nanoparticles produced at the presence of PVP, on the other hand, seems not to be markedly influenced by the silver precursor concentration. The values are always slightly above 100 nm, without following a particular tendency. The overall set of data nevertheless highlights the manufacturing of fairly uniform colloidal material.

3.3. Influence of the Polymer Concentration

The influence of the polymer concentration in the structural features of the manufactured silver colloids has been subsequently evaluated. The UV-vis patterns and dynamic light scattering data are portrayed in the Figure 7, and respective quantitative values are given in Table 3. Although the values of λ_{\max} are highly different comparing the synthesis of AgNPs stabilized by PVP and PEO-*b*-P2VP, which mainly reflects smaller sizes in the first case, the influence of the polymer concentration is not clearly evidenced in the final size of the silver colloids. The λ_{\max} does not follow a particular trend, and the dimension of the nanoparticles is always in the range $D_H \sim 13$ nm (AgNPs@PVP) or $D_H \sim 40$ nm (AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP).

Figure 7. UV-vis absorption spectra (top) and size distributions weighted by volume (bottom) for AgNPs@PVP (left) and AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP (right) prepared using different starting concentrations of the stabilizing polymers according to the legends.

The literature suggests that the concentration of the stabilizing polymer may be relevant and it might influence the final size of produced silver colloids. Nevertheless, there seem to be a threshold where above, almost no changes are observed. Whenever the polymer concentration is sufficient to stabilize the assemblies, no further influence might be clearly observed as similarly evidenced previously for polymer-stabilized AuNPs [34] and AgNPs.[35]

Table 3. Structural features as determined by UV-vis spectroscopy and light scattering measurements of polymer-stabilized AgNPs produced in a glass microfluidic device at different concentrations of the stabilizing polymers ($[\text{AgNO}_3] = 0.94 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$; $[\text{NaBH}_4] = 3.0 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$).

Polymer concentration (mmol.L ⁻¹)	D_H (nm)	ζ (mV)	λ_{max} (nm)	FWHM (nm)
AgNPs@PVP				
0.25	13.2 ± 0.3	-4 ± 1	398 ± 1	90 ± 4
0.50	13.2 ± 0.4	-26 ± 2	401.8 ± 0.5	111 ± 1
1.00	13.6 ± 0.4	-17 ± 2	403 ± 1	64 ± 4
2.50	13.0 ± 0.3	-7 ± 3	400.2 ± 0.6	76 ± 3
AgNPs@PEO-<i>b</i>-P2VP				
0.02	43 ± 1	$+8 \pm 2$	420 ± 1	114 ± 4
0.05	43 ± 1	$+11 \pm 2$	416 ± 2	105 ± 3
0.25	36 ± 2	$+12 \pm 1$	418.0 ± 0.7	98 ± 2
0.50	42 ± 1	$+13 \pm 2$	420 ± 2	80 ± 3

Nevertheless, the AgNPs stabilized by the block copolymer PEO-*b*-P2VP are notably bigger than those stabilized by PVP. The viscous forces are dominant over interfacial forces in laminar flows, and mass transfer depends purely on diffusion. The remarkable differences in particle size as influenced by the chemical nature of the polymeric shell might be linked the structural organization of the polymer chains in solution. The presence of a hydrophobic fraction (P2VP) in the PEO-*b*-P2VP block copolymer may conduct to the self-assembly of the chains at the interface between the precursor solutions, thus changing local viscosity, reducing diffusion rates, and increasing the final particle size as compared to PVP-stabilized AgNPs.

Additionally, the UV-vis patterns and the data reported in Table 3 evidences that higher polymer concentrations conduct overall to narrower particle size distribution (smaller values of FWHM). Indeed, the values are below 100 nm for the two highest polymer concentrations used in the manufacturing of the assemblies, regardless the

chemical nature of the stabilizer. There can be indeed noticed a consistent trend with regard to the values of FWHM for AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP, meaning that more homogenous samples are produced at higher polymer concentrations. Yet, this cannot be clearly observed by TEM probably because the number of probed particles is notably smaller compared to those probed by UV-vis. The TEM data are not shown for brevity taking into account the only marginal influence of the polymer concentration in the structural features of the produced silver colloids.

3.4. Influence of the Reducing Agent Concentration

The influence of the reducing agent concentration has been lastly evaluated. The data are reported in Figure 8 and Table 4.

Figure 8. UV-vis absorption spectra (top) and size distributions weighted by volume (bottom) for AgNPs@PVP (left) and AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP (right) prepared at different starting concentrations of the reducing agent according to the legend.

Table 4. Structural features as determined by UV-vis spectroscopy and dynamic light scattering measurements for polymer-stabilized AgNPs produced in a glass microfluidic device at different starting concentrations of NaBH₄ ([AgNO₃] = 0.94 mmol.L⁻¹ [PVP] = 0.5 mmol.L⁻¹; [PEO-*b*-P2VP] = 0.02 mmol.L⁻¹).

NaBH ₄ concentration (mmol.L ⁻¹)	R_H (nm)	ζ (mV)	λ_{max} (nm)	FWHM (nm)
AgNPs@PVP				
1.5	13.6 ± 0.1	- 24 ± 1	404.0 ± 1	79 ± 4
3.0	13.2 ± 0.4	- 26 ± 2	401.8 ± 0.5	111 ± 1
6.0	11.0 ± 0.5	- 27 ± 1	396.2 ± 0.7	107 ± 2
9.0	8.8 ± 0.9	- 24 ± 3	392.9 ± 0.9	50 ± 2
AgNPs@PEO-<i>b</i>-P2VP				
1.5	51 ± 3	+ 14 ± 3	421.9 ± 0.8	106 ± 2
3.0	43 ± 1	+ 8 ± 2	420 ± 1	114 ± 4
6.0	38.8 ± 0.4	+ 6 ± 2	408 ± 1	143 ± 7
9.0	37.6 ± 0.6	+ 7 ± 1	395.8 ± 0.7	187 ± 9

The influence of the NaBH₄ concentration is evidenced regardless the chemical nature of the stabilizing shell. Firstly, as NaBH₄ concentration increases, one monitors smaller values of λ_{max} which is consistence with the smaller values of R_H determined. The NaBH₄ is the responsible for the reduction of silver ions (Ag⁺) and, as one increases its amount in the environment, the silver nuclei are probably produced faster. The possible stabilization also by the excess of BH₄⁻ ions hampers nanoparticle growth thereby leading to smaller sizes.[36] These findings can also be explained by the high degree of stabilization provided by the PVP capping agent as similar reported in the stabilization of AuNPs.[34] The AgNPs stabilized by PEO-*b*-P2VP are more

polydisperse compared to those stabilized by PVP which can be explained by the rather weak capping agent feature which therefore does not inhibit the growth as much as PVP does. Indeed, for the highest amount of NaBH_4 used in the synthesis, the value of FWHM is even greater than 150 nm meaning fairly polydisperse colloidal systems. Additionally, there can be notice more asymmetric UV-vis profiles corroborating the synthesis of polydisperse particles in such conditions. Yet, although the value of λ_{max} is smaller than 400 nm, therefore suggesting the presence of much smaller particles, the monitored average R_H values are still in the range $R_H \sim 20$ nm. Nevertheless, one must take into account that the scattering of light is heavily weighted by particle volume and accordingly, a shift towards larger sizes compared to the UV-vis data is expected taking into account the asymmetric profiles.

Figure 9. TEM images (bottom) of AgNPs@PVP (left) and AgNPs@PEO-*b*-P2VP (right) prepared using the glass microfluidic device (see Figure 1) at starting concentrations of the reducing agent $[\text{NaBH}_4] = 9 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$ ($[\text{AgNO}_3] = 0.94 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$; $[\text{PVP}] = 0.5 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$; $[\text{PEO-}b\text{-P2VP}] = 0.02 \text{ mmol.L}^{-1}$).

The higher degree of heterogeneity of the AgNPs prepared in such experimental condition was confirmed by TEM observations (Figure 9). Particularly, the sample prepared using PEO-*b*-P2VP as the stabilizing agent and using the highest concentration of NaBH₄ (Figure 9B) evidences wider polydispersity, particles with different shapes, and also probably the presence of aggregates meaning that relatively low amount of the reducing agent should be used in order to fabricate more homogeneous spherical silver colloids.

4. Conclusions

We report the synthesis of uniform polymer-stabilized silver nanoparticles using microfluidic devices. The homogenous environment led to the formation of remarkably more uniform assemblies compared to those previously prepared in bulk, and therefore without control over the mixing conditions. The microfluidic-based method enabled the preparation of sub-50 nm AgNPs and their size can be to some extent tuned by the silver precursor concentration, although within a fairly narrow range. Regardless the polymer-stabilizing shell, the reducing agent concentration influences the size and polydispersity of the manufactured silver colloids, and relatively lower amounts allow for the manufacturing of more homogeneous nanoparticles. Remarkably, the use of the block copolymer PEO-*b*-P2VP as stabilizing agent conducted to notable larger AgNPs as evidenced by the higher values of λ_{\max} as well as larger values of the hydrodynamic dimension (R_H) compared to those stabilized by PVP. We judge this is a relevant new knowledge within the framework of polymer-stabilized AgNPs since a variety of other polymer chains can be used possibly with different outcomes regarding the final particle size. Therefore, these findings can guide to significant advances towards the manufacturing of polymer-coated metallic colloids, particularly when a target size is

required. Furthermore, the size distribution width can be narrowed by increasing the polymer concentration, although this variable does not have a distinguished effect on the final size of the manufactured silver colloids.

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